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Advaita and Adhyathma perspectives: The symbolic iconography of Sri Ganesha

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Abstract

The current understanding of the Hindu deity, Sri Ganesha, is full of popular misunderstandings. Western interpreters and Indologists cannot understand the symbolism behind an elephant headed God leading to malicious misinterpretations of Hindu divinity. Applying an objective framework to study Indian divinity leads to bizarre claims and nonsensical tropes. I propose a different approach from a native Hindu practitioners' perspective.

Because of a colonial hangover among western researchers, the perspectives of the native Hindu devotees and priests have been typically ignored in the Western understanding of Indian thought. The Advaita and Adhyathma interpretations of Vedanta state that the understanding of Sri Ganesha is filled with symbolism and spiritual meaning. The various facets of Sri Ganesha will be explored in detail. This article is a guide to genuine future researchers to apply more rigor, intellectual honesty, common sense and symbolism in the study of Indian divinity in Hindu, Buddhist and Jain faiths.

Keywords: Ganesha, Adhyathma, Advaita, Hindu, Buddhism, Jain

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1. Introduction

The elephant headed God of the Hindus has been a source of much hilarity and misunderstanding among non- Hindu researchers of Hindutva. They point out to mythology and evolutionary theory to state that none of these imagery can make any sense. Indian researchers have tried to reconcile the conflicting perspectives of the devotees and those of the western researchers by making extraordinary claims of Vedic plastic surgery, aliens etc. I argue that there is no need to reconcile Indian understanding of divinity with the Western conceptions of God. Both these perspectives are completely different. The Indian belief system is concerned with the subjective world and is full of nuanced symbolism. The Western religious framework is concerned with the objective world and nuance has little place. The West has to flip their perspective to truly understand Indian thought and not the other way around. These findings are equally true for the study of Buddhism and Jainism.

2. Discussion

3.1) The symbolism of Ganesha:

Ganesha symbolizes the inner power to overcome obstacles. It is the highest nature of the self that helps the ego overcome problems borne from foolish and short-sighted actions. That self lies within. Hence, people who pray to Ganesha thinking that he is merely an idol or external God, have little to no understanding of what he represents. Blessings may be had even if one does not see the Ganesha within, however one exalts one-self to a higher plane by understanding Ganesha the right way.

Ganesha is a manifestation of Mother Nature, also called Prakriti or Shakti. The story of Parvathi created Ganesha from her body is a lyrical way to state that he is an extended form of Mother Nature. Whatever the current generation believes or doesn't believe, they have to contend with the fact that Nature exists, and it is far-far bigger than they are. If Nature exists,

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Ganesha also exists. Both are equivalent. Therefore, in many pictures, he replaces his mother Parvathi. especially in the iconography of the three Shaktis as Tri-Ambikas.

3.2) The components of the iconography:

1) The elephant head:

Indian tales have to be reflected upon. The symbolic meaning is far more important than the literal meaning. Western thought has no room for symbolism, and hence it is understandable that they make no sense out of Hindu stories.

Ganesha is a tale of you and me. We are all born from the turmeric paste from the body of Prakriti. The turmeric paste refers to the skin and sweat of mother Earth, which represents soil and water. Every part of our body also belongs to Earth.

Most humans have no understanding of the connection between the body and consciousness, in this case Nature (Shakti) and the highest Atman consciousness (Shiva). They look upon both as separate forgetting that Shakti is Shiva and Shiva is Shakti. People who belittle and fight against the idea of consciousness will neither realize the divinity within. This is the significance of Ganesha safeguarding the threshold of Parvathi's palace and fighting with the forces of the highest Atman. Most of us keep fighting with our inner Atman guiding us in the right path. We rebel, fight and fail.

Finally, the head of an elephant represents the wisdom and power that an elephant represents. The human is the weakest terrestrial being on Earth, while the elephant is the largest and most powerful. By understanding the inner self (nature of Shiva), one transforms into being the most powerful living being. Every human being, without exception, is capable of this highest divinity. There are neither intermediaries nor interlocutors between you and the highest form.

2) The symbolism of the mouse as the mount:

The mouse represents you and me. Humans are eternally scampering around, in search of money, status, power etc. We are always running around everywhere, forever at the mercy of tyrants and bullies, who are just bigger mice compared to us. No mouse is truly courageous in the same way that no human, without understanding the nature of the Atman, can ever be truly brave. When we let Ganesha guide us, he points us not to material wealth but to inner wealth and prosperity. Thus, by knowing the Atman, one gets all the prosperity of the world.

These are recurrent symbolic themes - losing one's head and gaining the head of an elephant, mice losing their timidity by allowing Ganesha to be their master etc. The moral is the same - only by understanding inner divinity, can one truly progress in life and overcome Samsara. Every Dharmic tradition reinforces this idea again and again in countless stories. Look for this hidden meaning, the next time you read an Indian story. Now you will also understand why

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Jains and Buddhists also worship Ganesha. Once you know the symbolic meaning, everything makes perfect sense.

3) Big head and ears:

Ganesha represents the intelligence and intuition that guides the seeker to inner divinity. His big head denotes his great wisdom, and his large ears denote that he is ever attentive to those who seek him. No prayer goes unanswered.

4) The potbelly:

The pot belly does not really belong to him. It belongs to his earlier form, that of a human who went around fighting with the highest Atman. As we have seen earlier, the earlier form represents the unrealized human who does not know the highest truth. Such a person is prone to the gluttonous mindset of the ordinary human, that no desire can ever fulfil. Hence, the potbelly refers to our unmitigated quest for hedonistic pleasures. If one has a wise head, the potbelly or gluttonous body can no longer guide one's actions. Hence, become like Ganesha by making him your Guru.

5) Form of a child:

Ganesha is sometimes represented as a child when he is present with his mother. This means that our thoughts and desires have to mature, before we become truly independent. Growing older and becoming an adult does not mean becoming wise. Only when a person truly understands Advaita Vedanta (or Dvaita Vedanta), is a person truly mature and independent. Otherwise, the adult is merely a child. We see a lot of kidults in positions of authority, where they do not deserve to be. This lack of self-awareness is why the world is such a bad shape. Separately, the pot belly can also mean the ability to take away the selfish desires of the devotees into himself, so that the devotees can have an easier path towards self-realization.

6) Hands:

In his front two hands, one hand is in the Abhaya mudra denoting blessing and the other hand holding a lotus. Abhaya means courage, which I described earlier. The lotus denotes the flowering of consciousness. The lotus has to keep away from the muck of the world to flower above the muck.

In the two hands at the back, one holds Ankusha (goad) and another the Pasha (noose). The Ankusha is like an axe that defeats ego and pride. The pasha denotes the control of the wavering mind and the sense.

7) Tusks:

Tusks generally are used for attacking, but in Ganesha's case one is broken. The broken tusk means that the seeker of the Atman should never attack others to further his cause. The other

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tusk being whole means that one should defend their beliefs when under attack. Knowing when to practice non-violence (Ahimsa) and when not to practice Ahimsa is important. An elephant is neither completely gentle nor completely berserk. It calibrates its actions according to the situation.

8) Love for sweets:

Finally, the liking for sweets means that a realized being sees the problems of the world turning into sweets in front of them. AS devotees offer their problems to Ganesha, they turn to sweets. Problems reflect how the mind perceives the world. Once the mindset changes towards self-awareness, problems represent an opportunity.

3. Counter arguments

1) This is not how Indologists perceive Indian divinity

Indologists have been divorced from how Indian devotees perceive divinity. They are only in touch with English speaking devotees who are themselves as foreign to their own culture as the western researchers themselves. The Hindi and Sanskrit speaking worshippers can rarely communicate in English, and hence their perspective has been totally ignored. Being truthful to the devotee's perspectives is more important than being true to foreign Indologist perspectives.

2) Does this mean that symbolic Hindu understanding has no objective meaning?

Hindus also look at the objective world and consider it important, but the objective world is subordinate to the subjective world. I have touched on that problem in an earlier paper.¹ This is intuitive and closer to how each person lives their lived reality. The objective perspective of the world is a forced construct imposed on the human relation to the universe. The Hindu perception is therefore more fluid, dynamic and nuanced. This is in comparison to the scientific or western religious approaches, which are uncompromising and dogmatic about one reality.

3) Can there not be multiple symbolic representations of the icons of Hindu divinity? Is that a contradiction?

This question does not arise as Hindus believe in subjective reality. Subjective reality assumes that no two paths to the highest goal need to agree completely. Multiple interpretations are encouraged, and each seeker is asked to create one's own customized path. Everyone's karmic cycle is also different, and hence Karma is also neatly embedded in the subjective framework. The only distress is for western researchers who apply an objective framework, borrowed from the Abrahamic traditions, to study the Dharmic faiths. Such an exercise is doomed to failure.

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4. Conclusion

Native Hindus are highly distrustful of western researchers because their western academic accounts have no connection to how the devotees perceive their own spiritual universe. I have proposed a model of Advaita and Adhyathma symbolism to help bridge the gap. I have used the example of Sri Ganesha, a frequently misrepresented deity, to show how the gaps can be bridged. There is an inherent challenge to Indologists to reinvent their methodology for the 21st century, instead of relying on outdated British and German colonial perspectives towards Indian belief systems.

5. References

ⁱ Aravindakshan, V. (2025). Do we live in one single objective universe? The subjectivist challenge of Advaita Vedanta. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16472907>